

THE PROGRAM OF USING MODERN PEDAGOGICAL METHODS IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM AND THE PROBLEMS OF IMPROVING PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10044874>

Abstract. *In this article, the program for training pedagogical methods based on modern mobile and information technologies in the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan provides information about the methods of teaching various subjects in higher education. The main goal of this article is to provide practical recommendations on increasing pedagogical potential in the higher education system and increasing students' interest in science. The authors conducted a survey among university students and the students expressed their opinions. in the Republic of Uzbekistan describes the list of the most effective mobile technologies and the correct formation of information using "modern pedagogical education based on technologies". Currently, information dissemination and gathering technologies are used in the creation of pedagogical methods will consist of collecting interesting information about Internet resources, video Internet communication tools and science.*

Keywords: *pedagogical skill, pedagogical potential, modern educational program, technologies in education, pedagogical analysis.*

Introduction

To date as we live in the era of advanced technologies, we believe that the demand for technologies in most fields is very high in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The current modern stage of the development of the higher education system in the Republic of Uzbekistan showed the need to increase the quality of education and the capacity of teachers, increase the number of new methods. From teachers for this it will be necessary to develop methods of research and new science based on mobility and integration processes in world experiences. Modern the main goal of innovations in the educational program is to develop the motivational skills of the teacher. Pedagogical methods are mainly described in technology-based methods student's actions, independent orientation of received information, formation of creative thinking it consists of showing the priority directions of using the latest achievements of science and technology. Today, in the higher education system, we believe that the activity of the teacher and the organization of education should be carried out with high pedagogical skills. By the present time, in the information society, knowledge and skills have become the priority values of human life. In the modern educational program, education is carried out through mobile technologies - means of mobile communication between people. As for improving pedagogical and psychological skills, the following mobile technologies can be effective in improving the quality of lessons. These are e-mail service, interesting science information and wiki technologies, electronic dictionaries, synchronous video Internet connection, use of navigators will further increase the quality of the lesson. Traditionally, the main course aimed at teaching and explaining the science of pedagogy

and psychology for students of Karakalpak State University and translating special texts, as well as teaching the features of the syntax of the scientific method can be implemented with a curriculum according to the educational standard. These are modern methods in the higher education system based on teaching and increasing students' interest in science. Currently, modern libraries and computer training for university students are implemented in various forms. Innovations start from the change of the educational process, equipping the classrooms with modern technical tools to various aspects of the educational process and testing new educational technologies in the process of self-training of students in practical training became the opinion of a large number of students. Based on the opinions of students, a survey was organized and in the modern education system expressed the conclusions that the technology of mixed education (or an educational program organized on the basis of mixed education) allows organizing the most effective time of the teacher and the teacher. A few students thought of implementing a technology-enabled curriculum makes the process interesting and comfortable. This will increase students' interest in science and gain new knowledge. The main goal of teachers is to provide quality education to students. My opinion is that in today's higher education system, it is necessary to establish a curriculum based on the wishes of students. Most of the students' opinions are that "the lesson processes are boring" or "we did not understand the information given by the teacher". We don't blame the teacher for this, but neither does the student. Because the teacher gave the students the information he knew, we can conclude that the student could not keep the information in his memory or did not understand the information. The system will never produce an efficient result from this. The students only waste 90 minutes of their time, and the teacher gets paid by the hour of the lesson, not by the quality of the lesson. So why is the higher education system the way it is? The idea of students is to use new information using modern technologies to improve the quality of lessons and provide more access to interesting information about science. Teaching requires pedagogical skills and potential from the teacher. Some teachers read the information from the book for 90 minutes. Some teachers have 90 minutes to write the information in the book to the student. Some teachers are busy with their work during the 90 minutes, while the students sit on their phones doing what they know. From this we can conclude that both the teacher and the student are indifferent to the lesson. The reason is that the education system is outdated. In the imagination of both the teacher and the student is the end of the lesson and the return to the next lesson or home. This creates ignorance. And the student will be an uneducated specialist tomorrow when he graduates from the university or will not be able to work in any enterprise. If the higher education system continues like this, there will be more uneducated specialists. it is necessary to re-introduce the education system. In this regard, a system of retraining of pedagogic personnel and a system of improving computer literacy of pedagogic personnel should be established. In higher education, the pedagogue is responsible for the quality of the lesson. The use of different methods in science will further increase the interest of students. New computer methods, slides and videos on the topic should be used in the process of teaching students to improve pedagogical skills and potential. The subject should come before the student's eyes. Their opinions should be heard, students should exchange ideas with each other. It is necessary to help the students to remember the information they need and to learn the information they do not understand. During the lesson, the teacher should organize various interesting discussions and games on the topic. This increases the student's interest in science. But there is a question whether the teacher has the knowledge to give the student enough knowledge? Teachers should use different methods to make

students interested in science. Although 40% of the information remains in the student's memory, 30% of the information is learned in independent study or in a laboratory setting. In general, I think that the teacher should deliver 70% of knowledge to the student perfectly. However, one of the most observed cases in higher education today is the involvement of students in various activities and ceremonies during class time. Here, students fill the hall during the ceremony and clap during the ceremony. Who or what is a student for higher education institutions? In the higher education system, we express different relations in the program of training of pedagogic personnel. For example: Currently, national and international language certificates are mandatory for candidates admitted to the master's degree. For example: a person with a local certificate of language proficiency B2 can be admitted to a master's program, but does he have knowledge in his specialty? For example: I graduated from university this year, I have a great interest in my specialty, and I have a high level of education, but I do not have a language certificate. So I will not be admitted to the master's exam. Well, let's say I got a B2 language certificate to enter a master's degree. I have been admitted to the master's program, why do I need a language certificate? Do I teach students in English? Do students understand if I teach in English:)? A language certificate only serves as a ticket, for example, tomorrow I want to fly on a plane and I need to get a ticket. I arrived at my destination on the plane and I no longer need that ticket and I can no longer use the ticket. In the higher education system, we should develop programs to provide students with a high level of knowledge and to improve the quality of education. For example, teachers in schools have their own methods in subjects. Various subjects, such as mathematics, chemistry, and physics, have the main goal of improving students' understanding of these subjects. The school has its own methodology for each subject. It is the most important task of all parents and teachers to raise our young people to be educated, intelligent and loyal to their country. We need to convey our national values and great history to our youth. In the higher education system, it was mentioned that teachers should allocate time correctly. The teacher conducts lessons based on the set hours. During the lesson, 50 minutes should be planned for explaining the topic and answering students' questions, 20 minutes for discussion and conversation on the topic, and 15 minutes for answering questions on the topic. Quality and meaningful course of the lesson depends on the capacity of the teacher and the attention of the students. Teachers can organize interesting competitions on the topic at the end of the lesson. This will further increase the interest of students. I witnessed the teaching process of the teachers. Some teachers hold interesting competitions on the topic. Some teachers enhance the quality of the lesson by introducing science terms or information. Lessons are very enjoyable. This leads to further expansion of the teacher's pedagogical activity. Teachers should develop an explanation method for each topic. The teacher should conduct a pedagogical analysis of students' acquisition of knowledge.

Conclusion

As a pedagogue, I have conducted many studies on the psychological condition of students and the pedagogical skills of teachers. In the higher education system of Uzbekistan, teachers try their best to train qualified personnel and find their place in the future. Based on the interests of the students, we came to the conclusion. During the lesson, it is necessary to cover the topics through technological knowledge, so that the students can remember the information related to the topic. In the course of the lesson, attention should be drawn only to the acquisition of new knowledge. I think that from now on, we should pay attention to providing quality education to

students in the higher education system and to the system of retraining pedagogic personnel in higher education. If the students' interests are taken into account during the lesson, the students will be able to learn a lot of new knowledge. It is necessary to use new pedagogical methods on the subject. New methods will be the best way for the teacher to explain the subject.

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